

Cybersecurity Threat Modeling and Risk Mitigation for PID Systems in Open Science - Part 1

Many often wonder why PIDs, especially for objects, come at a fee. The argument that open access should make them free sounds appealing but is not realistic. When I was the director of IT for an actuarial firm, I realised that nothing can be free if the offering is to be sustained and maintained perpetually. The infrastructure, security, and human resources required would need funding to keep the 'freebie' alive. Moreover, there are bad actors in the digital world ready to compromise the confidentiality, integrity, and availability of such infrastructure if it is not well maintained. According to [NIST](#), the CIA triad consists of **confidentiality**, which involves the protection of important assets from unauthorised persons; **integrity**, which ensures the content of the asset is not compromised; and **availability**, which ensures access to the asset when needed. In this short article, I will provide a little insight into scenarios related to confidentiality.

According to [Westminster](#), "Persistent Identifiers (PIDs) aim to be a unique long-lasting reference to digital objects of various types, and are a core element of open research." Broadly, there are two categories of PIDs: PIDs for objects and PIDs for persons. I mentioned objects as defined by [Westminster](#) because other categories fall under objects. For instance, a place, research activities, research outputs, and many other inanimate objects are all forms of objects. In this article, I will introduce my expert knowledge in technology, cybersecurity, open science, and digital innovations to build a case for cybersecurity for PID systems. [Chodacki and Carpenter \(2024\)](#) identified some elements of PIDs as being unique, persistent, resolvable, and globally accessible with metadata linkage.

From a threat perspective, every element mentioned is a potential threat surface. The infrastructure that holds PIDs requires great attention to maintain the confidentiality of identity and access management (IAM) within the infrastructure. One common way of compromising the confidentiality of any digital resource is through authentication and access control. When a PID registration agency creates access for an entity to create a DOI, the entity has the responsibility to safeguard the credentials. The transmission of credentials must be secure through appropriate security protocols. For instance, it could be through email but with other validation methods. It is important to note that if the authentication process is compromised, the entity should promptly reset the password or notify the registration agency.

Many organisations are now moving to passwordless systems as recommended by [NIST](#). By passwordless, [NIST](#) encourages the adoption of multi-factor authentication (MFA), combining a minimum of two authentication methods to access a digital resource, depending on the criticality and security classification of the object being protected. These factors include what you know (e.g., your password or passphrase), what you have (e.g., a hardware token, an authentication app, or a token sent to your device or email), and what you are (e.g., biometric, iris scan, or retina scan).

Since most PID infrastructures are cloud-based, care should be taken by both the infrastructure provider and the infrastructure user. In most cases, a system compromise occurs on the user's end. It could be due to a compromised computer, which the user may not be aware of, or carelessness with authentication credentials. In rare cases, a provider's infrastructure could be the target of an advanced persistent threat (APT) attack. In both scenarios, a proper threat mitigation strategy must be in place to address the threat landscape. Social engineering, where bad actors pretend to be allies in order to retrieve authentication credentials through various methods, or an infected computer or digital device that can be accessed remotely by bad actors or transmit credentials to a command centre, as well as cross-site scripting or man-in-the-middle attacks, can all be exploited.

To reduce the threat landscape, continuous cybersecurity awareness is required for both the provider's staff and infrastructure users through various campaigns. Endpoint security for all users should be encouraged, and regular patches for all devices should be a standard practice. At a minimum, AES (Advanced Encryption Standard) protocol should be supported by network devices used to access PID infrastructure to reduce network threats, while zero-day exploits can be mitigated with up-to-date patches. On the backend, developers should consider containerization for agile delivery of solutions to contain threats. Code reviews should be a regular practice, while audit trails should be well monitored with advanced tools capable of identifying unusual user activities.

The good news is that most registration agencies are now cloud-based, and top cloud service providers have already deployed several threat mitigation solutions in their infrastructure.

A preview of my next short blog could be related to the imaginary story below: Dr. Lagbaja was a prolific writer for Tamedu Institute (both names are fictional). During his time with Tamedu, Lagbaja's papers and datasets were assigned DOIs, which were maintained by the institution. As time passed, Tamedu faced challenges and closed down. All of Dr. Lagbaja's DOIs were still available online until the domain name of Tamedu's institute expired, and the DOIs became dead links. Fast forward a couple of years, and another researcher needed to reference Lagbaja's work and access the data but could no longer do so. Is it possible to manipulate metadata? I will share more on this in Part 2, addressing the integrity of PIDs.